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D5.1 AI Tools and Technologies V1

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
API	Application Programming Interface
BDV	Big Data Value
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
Byte-Pair Encoding	Byte-Pair Encoding
CNN	Convolution Neural Networks
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	DataBase
DeBERTa	Decoding-enhanced BERT with Disentangled Attention
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named-Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
POS	Part of Speech
RA	Reference Architecture
REST	Representational State Transfer
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
RoBERTa	Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
SVMs	Support Vector Machines
VM	Virtual Machine
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable AI
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive summary

This document (D5.1 AI Tools and Technologies V1”) was developed within the framework of WP5 “Cloud-based AI Tools for Citizen Centric & Autonomous Policy Making”. In D5.1 we summarize the work of T5.1 and T5.2 that aims to develop advanced AI tools for providing text and sentiment analysis, exploiting both structured and unstructured data (e.g., conversations, declarations or even tweets).

In this first version of the D5.1 we will focus on the sentiment analysis and opinion mining component. For this component a REST Application Programming Interface (API) has been developed by Reportbrain, to provide the sentiment and emotion from citizens’ feedback, of the text extracted from either Tweets or comments. This tool will be integrated to the VPME (Virtualized Policy Management Environment) platform, as citizens’ feedback analysis is the layer to support interactions between policymakers and citizens. This technology aims to provide data-based insights using opinion mining and to convert the unstructured online information provided by the Pilots, into a great asset for the policymakers.

The deliverable discusses the classification models that have been deployed for the sentiment and emotion analysis, as well as the component’s architecture, and focuses on the implementation of this analysis to Pilots’ data and sources. The sentiment analysis models specialize in polarity (positive, negative, neutral) but also in emotions (anger, joy, sadness, etc.).

This NLP technology can analyse citizens’ feedback from both implicit (e.g., through the data obtained from social media) and explicit (e.g., online surveys for proposed policies, utilization of municipalities’ applications, etc.) sources, and provide those insights to the policymakers and local governments.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e. AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of Work Package 5

WP5 will deliver a set of AI solutions and the core outcome of the project, the Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will integrate an open environment for analytics and will provide the unique point for policymakers to access resources. Thus, the main objectives of this WP are to:

- (i) Analyse various datasets to obtain actionable insights through AI tools that range from sentiment analysis and text analytics to opinion mining and policy recommendations.
- (ii) Include citizens in the loop of policies implementation through a citizen-centric approach to obtain feedback and continuously evaluate and optimize the policies.
- (iii) Deliver the policy management environment (VPME) for creating, customizing, linking / comparing, simulating, evaluating and optimizing policies.
- (iv) Provide the required computing and data resources for performing the aforementioned AI analytics by dynamically allocating the required cloud resources.

1.3 Relation to other WPs and tasks

WP3, WP4, WP5 are the core technical work-packages of the project, which focus on three independent and complementary streams of technological work driven by the technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture provided by WP2.

WP5 integrates the results from WP3 and WP4 with the AI tools, the Open Analytical environment and the citizens-centric optimization and provides to the Pilot tasks of WP6 the interfaces to access resources and interact with the Platform.

Finally WP5 feeds WP7 with the AI tools and the AI-based policy making artefacts (e.g. AI pipelines and AI models) for the Market Platform and WP8 with useful content to disseminate the AI-based policy making approach.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.4 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable addresses the first of the WP5 objectives reported above, presenting the AI tools and technologies that have been deployed to perform sentiment analysis, opinion mining and text analytics. These technologies have been used to provide the citizens’ feedback analysis to the AI4PublicPolicy project.

1.5 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The **first chapter** of the document is an introduction to the project and the document.
- The **second chapter** of the document is the background and state-of-the-art of Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining techniques and models that have been deployed for this task
- The **third chapter** of the document presents the solution design
- The **fourth chapter** demonstrates the API (Application Programming Interface) and its implementation in the Pilots municipalities examples
- Finally, the document includes a **fifth chapter** with the conclusions

2 Background and State of the Art

2.1 Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining

The use of natural language processing and opinion mining methods has been utilized throughout the last years through sentiment analysis to detect, obtain, compute, and examine information by organizations, in order to evaluate and improve their customer feedback (Soussan T. & Trovati M., 2022). There has been a rise in the accessibility of online applications and a surge in social platforms for opinion sharing and online reviews, which have captured the attention of stakeholders such as customers, organizations, and governments to analyse and explore these opinions (Saberri B. & Saad S., 2017).

The purpose of the Sentiment Analysis component is to provide the sentiment of citizens' feedback to the Pilots Municipalities, exploiting data from conversations, declarations or even tweets. To process the extensive content collected from Pilots' different data sources, the sentiment of each sentence/body is evaluated using complex Machine Learning models as well as robust and load-balanced data processing pipelines. The sentiment analysis models specialize in polarity (positive, negative, neutral) but also in emotions (anger, joy, sadness, etc.).

The input data is in raw text format. The data then is processed using the NLP pipeline for text classification that has been developed for this task. The task aims to the improvement of evidence-based policy making, leveraging the huge amount of user-generated content that exists in multiple external sources beyond government websites and social media accounts, to support the formulation of public policies.

For the citizens' sentiment analysis in the AI4PublicPolicy project, Reportbrain deployed classification methods, as well as transformers and BERTt-like models, that will be described and demonstrated below in this document.

2.2 Text Classification

Text classification is a construction problem of models which can classify new documents into predefined classes. It is a sophisticated process involving not only the training of models, but also numerous additional procedures, e.g., data pre-processing, transformation, and dimensionality reduction. Text classification remains a prominent research topic, utilizing various techniques and their combinations in complex systems (Mirończuk M. & Protasiewicz J., 2018). One of the most popular forms of text classification is sentiment analysis, which assigns a label like positive, negative, or neutral to a sequence of text. To exact inference on a text, tokenization and a model method need to be chosen.

2.2.1 Sentiment Classification

Sentiment Analysis is a major task in the Natural Language Processing (NLP) field that classifies the polarity of a given text. It is used to understand the sentiments of the customer/people for products, services or topics and helps companies and organizations to understand the feedback.

The work of sentiment analysis has focused on topical categorization, attempting to sort documents according to their subject matter. However, recent years have seen rapid growth in online discussions and reviews, where a crucial characteristic of the posted comments is their sentiment or overall opinion towards the subject matter. Labelling these comments with their sentiment provides succinct summaries to readers. Sentiment classification is also helpful in business intelligence

applications and recommender systems (Terveen et al. (1997), Tatemura (2000)), where user input and feedback can be quickly summarized. Indeed, free-form survey responses given in natural language format can be processed using sentiment categorization.

The task investigates how applicable sentiment analysis techniques can improve evidence-based policymaking. In addition to information on government websites, the sentiment analysis can be performed on the huge amount of user-generated content that exists in multiple external online sources.

2.2.2 Emotion Classification

Emotion classification is similar to sentiment analysis. It classifies the polarity of a given text, but instead of only having three distinct classes - positive, negative and neutral - it breaks down into smaller classes of positive and negative emotions. The emotion classification focuses on primary emotions such as sadness, joy, neutral, anger, disgust and surprise. Emotion classification, or emotion categorization, classifies any given input as 'neutral ' or as one of several given emotions that best represent the mental state of the subject's facial expression, words, and so on.

3 Solution Design

Focusing on how to involve citizens in the process and use their feedback for local governments to develop more citizen-centric policies, we have designed a REST Application Programming Interface (API), deploying pre-trained models for sentiment, as well as emotion analysis. This solution is designed for the purpose of analysing the text of the Pilots' sources that contain citizens' comments, complaints, recommendations and more, and extracts the sentiment of the text to convert it into actionable insights for the policymakers.

The basic idea is to start with a tool that can accurately analyse the comments and tweets provided by citizens in the Pilots municipalities and to expand this tool to even further data sources as we move forward with the project. The solution currently designed for this task includes different types of deep learning models incorporated in the inference pipeline.

The internal architecture was designed to take all information into consideration with minimal user input, thus most of the procedures are happening under the hood and they are not visible to the user. There are three selection parameters to achieve the optimal result for each case – language (en, it, el, pt, bg), task (sentiment, emotion) and context (Twitter, comments). The user has to choose the task and the context since this cannot be inferred programmatically. However, they do not have to provide a language since there is a very accurate language identification model in place. Thus, considering all these parameters {context, task, language} the API has independent endpoints that correspond to the optimal model that is chosen internally.

This section is organized as follows: First the demonstrator is contextualized in the Reference Architecture of the project. Then “Model components” describes a breakdown of the model's usage and “Pipeline” provides an overview of the whole procedure behind an API call. Finally, Application Programming Interface Architecture describes the operation details to make an API call.

3.1 Mapping on the Reference Architecture

This first version of the demonstrator implements the “Sentiment Analysis” module in the AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture. It is integrated with the “Policy Extraction” and “Policy

Evaluation” modules, providing sentiment analysis capabilities in the data analysis and stakeholders’ feedback evaluation.

Figure 2. Mapping to the Reference Architecture

3.2 Model Components

The pipeline selects a particular pre-trained model that has been fine-tuned for sentiment or emotion analysis. There are three main steps involved when some text passes to a pipeline:

1. Tokenizer: The raw text is preprocessed.
2. Model: The preprocessed inputs are passed to the model.
3. Postprocessing: The predictions of the model are post-processed, into comprehensible classes

The following figure - Model Components (Figure 2) displays the three main steps and how the model works. For example, the input of “I love NLP” has been classified as positive with 99.04% probability. A detailed description of the individual steps will be provided below.

Figure 3. Model Components

3.2.1 Tokenizer

Like other neural networks, Transformer models cannot process raw text directly, so the first step of our pipeline is to convert the text inputs into numbers that the model can understand. Tokenizing a text is splitting it into words or subwords, which then are converted to IDs (Figure 2) through a look-up table. Converting words or subwords to IDs is straightforward. Some common tokenization techniques that are used in transformers-models are Byte-Pair Encoding (BPE), WordPiece, SentencePiece etc.

Space and punctuation tokenization and rule-based tokenization are both examples of word tokenization, which is loosely defined as splitting sentences into words. While it is the most intuitive way to split texts into smaller chunks, this tokenization method can lead to problems for massive text corpora. In this case, space and punctuation tokenization usually generates a very big vocabulary. Such a big vocabulary size forces the model to have an enormous embedding matrix as the input and output layer, which causes both an increased memory and time complexity.

On the other hand, character tokenization is very simple and would greatly reduce memory and time complexity, it makes it much harder for the model to learn meaningful input representations. Therefore, character tokenization is often accompanied by a loss of performance. To get the best of both worlds, transformers models use a hybrid between word-level and character-level tokenization called subword tokenization.

Subword tokenization algorithms rely on the principle that frequently used words should not be split into smaller subwords, but rare words should be decomposed into meaningful subwords. Subword tokenization allows the model to have a reasonable vocabulary size while being able to learn meaningful context-independent representations. In addition, subword tokenization enables the model to process words it has never seen before, by decomposing them into known subwords.

A tokenizer takes care of preparing the inputs for a model. Tokenization methods map between the original string (character and words) and the token space (e.g., getting the index of the token comprising a given character or the span of characters corresponding to a given token). For example, as we displayed in Figure 2, the original string “I Love NLP!” is converted to the token space [0, 100, 657, 21992, 328, 2].

The tokenizer returns a dictionary with three important items:

- **input_ids** are the indices corresponding to each token in the sentence.
- **attention_mask** indicates whether a token should be attended to or not.
- **token_type_ids** identifies which sequence a token belongs to when there is more than one sequence.

The `input_ids` can be decoded to return the original input. All pre-processing needs to be done in exactly the same way as when the model was pretrained.

3.2.2 Model

This architecture contains only the base Transformer module: given some inputs, it outputs what we'll call *hidden states*, also known as *features*. For each model input, we'll retrieve a high-dimensional vector representing the **contextual understanding of that input by the Transformer model**.

A high-dimensional vector is the vector output (see Figure 2) by the Transformer module, which is usually large. It generally has three dimensions:

- **Batch size:** The number of sequences processed at a time
- **Sequence length:** The length of the numerical representation of the sequence
- **Hidden size:** The vector dimension of each model input.

It is said to be “high dimensional” because of the last value. The hidden size can be very large.

Transformers and BERT-like models

A transformer is a deep learning model that adopts the mechanism of self-attention, differentially weighting the significance of each part of the input data. Like recurrent neural networks (RNNs), transformers are designed to process data such as natural language. However, unlike RNNs which process the input sequentially (Figure 3), transformers process the entire input all at once (Figure 4). The attention mechanism provides context for any position in the input sequence. For example, if the input data is a natural language sentence, the transformer does not have to process one word at a time. This allows for more parallelization than RNNs and therefore reduces training times.

Bidirectional Encoder Representation for Transformer (BERT) is an NLP model developed by Google Research in 2018 (Devlin et al 2018), after its inception, it has achieved state-of-the-art accuracy on several NLP tasks. Transformer architecture has an encoder and decoder stack, hence called encoder-decoder architecture whereas BERT is just an encoder stack of transformer architecture. There are two variants, BERT-base and BERT-large, which differ in architecture complexity. The base model has 12 layers in the encoder whereas the Large has 24 layers. Figure 3 shows its bidirectional architecture as compared to other language models. BERT was trained on a large text corpus, which gives architecture/model the ability to better understand the language and to learn variability in data patterns and generalizes well on several NLP tasks. As it is bidirectional that means BERT learns information from both the left and the right side of a token's context during the training phase. Bert pretrained using a combination of masked language modeling objective and next sentence prediction on a large corpus comprising the Toronto Book Corpus and Wikipedia. Unlike previous language representation models, BERT is designed to pre-train deep bidirectional representations from unlabeled text by jointly conditioning on both left and right context in all layers. As a result, the pre-trained BERT model can be fine-tuned with just one additional output layer to create state-of-the-art models for a wide range of tasks, such as question answering and language inference, without substantial task-specific architecture modifications.

Figure 4. RNN Architecture

Figure 5. Bert Architecture

BERT has inspired many variants, two of the most important ones are RoBERTa and DeBERTA.

RoBERTa

The RoBERTa model was proposed in “RoBERTa: A Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach” by Liu et al. 2019. It builds on BERT and modifies key hyperparameters, removing the next-sentence pretraining objective and training with much larger mini-batches and learning rates. RoBERTa builds on BERT’s language masking strategy, wherein the system learns to predict intentionally hidden sections of text within otherwise unannotated language examples. RoBERTa, which was implemented in PyTorch, modifies key hyperparameters in BERT, including removing BERT’s next-sentence pretraining objective and training with much larger mini-batches and learning rates. This allows RoBERTa to improve on the masked language modelling objective compared with BERT and leads to better downstream task performance.

BERT training procedure can significantly improve its performance on a variety of NLP tasks while also indicating that this overall approach remains competitive with alternative approaches. More broadly, this research further demonstrates the potential for self-supervised training techniques to match or exceed the performance of more traditional, supervised approaches. RoBERTa is part of Facebook’s ongoing commitment to advancing state-of-the-art self-supervised systems that can be developed with less reliance on time- and resource-intensive data labelling. We look forward to seeing what the wider community does with the model and code for RoBERTa.

This implementation is the same as BertModel with tiny embedding tweaks as well as a setup for Roberta pretrained models. RoBERTa has the same architecture as BERT but uses a byte-level

BPE as a tokenizer (same as GPT-2) and uses a different pretraining scheme. RoBERTa doesn't have `token_type_ids`, you don't need to indicate which token belongs to which segment.

DeBERTa

The DeBERTa model was proposed in the novel paper “DeBERTa: Decoding-enhanced BERT with Disentangled Attention” by He et al. 2020. It builds on RoBERTa with disentangled attention and enhanced mask decoder training with half of the data used in RoBERTa. DeBERTa (Decoding-enhanced BERT with disentangled attention) improves the BERT and RoBERTa models using two novel techniques. The first is the disentangled attention mechanism, where each word is represented using two vectors that encode its content and position, respectively, and the attention weights among words are computed using disentangled matrices on their contents and relative positions. Second, an enhanced mask decoder is used to replace the output softmax layer to predict the masked tokens for model pretraining.

3.2.3 Postprocessing

The values we get as output from our model do not necessarily make sense by themselves. Those values are not probabilities but logits, the raw, unnormalized scores outputted by the last layer of the model. To be converted to probabilities (see Figure 2), they need to go through a SoftMax layer (all Transformers models output the logits, as the loss function for training will generally fuse the last activation function, such as SoftMax, with the actual loss function, such as cross-entropy). The probability score is not to be confused with rule-based methodologies that show the percentage of positive over total words. In this case, the probability shows “how sure we are that this input belongs in this category”. For example, a text that has a 90% probability score is not more positive than a text that has 80% probability score, but in the former we are more sure the specific input belongs in this category than the later.

3.3 Pipeline

The pipeline (Figure 4) encapsulates the complete procedure behind every api endpoint. The procedure starts as follows: the user inputs the raw text, and the text goes through a language identification procedure.

Language Identification: uses a probabilistic n-gram rule-based engine of sizes 1 up to 5. This engine first determines the alphabet of the input text and searches for characters which are unique in one or more languages. The rule-based engine filters out languages that do not satisfy the conditions of the input text. This method performs better from models that are trained on character distribution, especially when the input text is very small (one or two word sentence), which is very common in twitter.

Then according to the language identified the input text is routed to the appropriate model (internally), thus the user does not have to choose among languages and models. The architecture is the same for each endpoint but trained in a different language. Finally, the result output is the class with respective probability scores.

Figure 6. Pipeline Flow

3.4 Application Programming Interface (API) Architecture

The API design conforms to the constraints of the REST architectural style and provides a great deal of flexibility for the user. All requests are POST requests and return the result as JSON output. Since the API is publicly available, an X-API-KEY header (secret) is being used as an authentication technique, to authenticate incoming requests and avoid usage from unauthorized users. The authentication is possible to be changed into JSON Web Token (JWT) when the API will be fully incorporated in the VPME.

The architecture of the API aims to be very easy to interact with since all endpoints only require a “text” argument to be completed in the body of the request. The pre-processing of the text is achieved with tokenization, which converts text input into numbers that the model can understand. Providing the text, the API recognizes the language and redirects the appropriate model under the hood, without additional input from the user’s side. After the model evaluation, the output post-processing decodes the result into distinct human-readable classes and returns it in JSON format.

Input

Raw text from different pilots’ sources e.g., citizens’ tweets, comments from various platforms, complaints, reports, or surveys.

Output

The result of the API is in JSON format, where it contains the:

- Identified language
- Predicted class of the emotion or sentiment analysis
- Associated probability score of the prediction
- Initial text

4 Implementation

All the available API endpoints and the models used in each endpoint irrespective of the language will be described in this section, accompanied by examples. We split the analysis and demonstration by the type of source (comments or Twitter), by language and by task, which in this case is the sentiment and emotion classifications. In the examples, we will display the secret API KEY as \$TOKEN to avoid non-authorized usage. The token will be provided by RBP until the integration into VPME where the token generation will be available throughout the platform.

4.1 Comments

Comments analytics focuses on opinions posted by users about a particular entity. Both sentiment and emotion analysis is created with the Roberta model technology and the available languages are English(en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), and Bulgarian (bg). The available endpoints and classes of each model can be found below:

Endpoint: `/sentiment/comments`

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: `/emotion/comments`

- Labels: anger, disgust, joy, neutral, sadness, surprise

Example 1

In the first example, a comment from the Genoa Pilot database in the Italian language has been provided as input in the API request, to the comments endpoints for both sentiment and emotion.

We can see the output in the API response, separately for sentiment and emotion. The text has been identified as Italian. In the sentiment response, the text has been classified as “negative” with a score of 99%, while in the emotion response the detected emotion is “sadness” with a score of 99%.

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/sentiment/comments' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
  "text": "Buongiorno Vi segnalo lo stato di degrado nel quale versano le scale di accesso di
  Via Fieschi al Palazzo del Consiglio Regionale, materiale abbandonato, un bici abbandonata e
  scalini rovinati. Grazie per ripristino dei gradini per salvaguardare l''incolumità dei
  pedoni. Saluti Badino"
}'
```

Comment translation from Italian to English:

Hello I would like to point out the state of decay in which the access stairs of Via Fieschi to the Palazzo del Consiglio Regionale fall, abandoned material, an abandoned bike and ruined steps. Thank you for restoring the steps to safeguard the safety of pedestrians. Greetings

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "it",
  "label": "negative",
  "score": 0.9998,
  "text": "Buongiorno Vi segnalo lo stato di degrado nel quale versano le scale di accesso di
  Via Fieschi al Palazzo del Consiglio Regionale, materiale abbandonato, un bici abbandonata e
  scalini rovinati. Grazie per ripristino dei gradini per salvaguardare l'incolumità dei pedoni.
  Saluti Badino"
}
```

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/emotion/comments' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
  "text": "Buongiorno Vi segnalo lo stato di degrado nel quale versano le scale di accesso di
Via Fieschi al Palazzo del Consiglio Regionale, materiale abbandonato, un bici abbandonata e
scalini rovinati. Grazie per ripristino dei gradini per salvaguardare l''incolumità dei
pedoni. Saluti Badino"
}'
```

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "it",
  "label": "sadness",
  "score": 0.9952608942985535,
  "text": "Buongiorno Vi segnalo lo stato di degrado nel quale versano le scale di accesso di
Via Fieschi al Palazzo del Consiglio Regionale, materiale abbandonato, un bici abbandonata e
scalini rovinati. Grazie per ripristino dei gradini per salvaguardare l'incolumità dei pedoni.
Saluti Badino"
}
```

Example 2

In example 2, a comment from the Burgas Pilot database in the Bulgarian language has been provided as input in the API request, to the comments endpoints for both sentiment and emotion.

In the output of the API responses, the sentiment of the text has been classified as “negative” with a 90% score and the detected emotion is “anger” with 59% score. The language of the text has been identified as Bulgarian.

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/sentiment/comments' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
  "text": "Моля, направете нещо с идиоти с премахнаха заглушители, огромни скорости и луди
шумни коли и мотоциклети. Градът (и в частност ул. Гурко и Цар Симеон) се е превърнал в
автопътека за умствено изостанали от всякакъв вид и тип."
}'
```

Comment translation from Bulgarian to English:

Please do something about idiots with removed mufflers, huge speeds and crazy loud cars and motorbikes. The city (and Gurko and Tsar Simeon streets in particular) has become a freeway for the mentally retarded of all kinds and types.

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "bg",
  "label": "negative",
  "score": 0.9076,
  "text": "Моля, направете нещо с идиоти с премахнаха заглушители, огромни скорости и луди шумни коли и мотоциклети. Градът (и в частност ул. Гурко и Цар Симеон) се е превърнал в автопътека за умствено изостанали от всякакъв вид и тип."
}
```

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/emotion/comments' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Моля, направете нещо с идиоти с премахнаха заглушители, огромни скорости и луди шумни коли и мотоциклети. Градът (и в частност ул. Гурко и Цар Симеон) се е превърнал в автопътека за умствено изостанали от всякакъв вид и тип"
  }'
```

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "bg",
  "label": "anger",
  "score": 0.59,
  "text": "Моля, направете нещо с идиоти с премахнаха заглушители, огромни скорости и луди шумни коли и мотоциклети. Градът (и в частност ул. Гурко и Цар Симеон) се е превърнал в автопътека за умствено изостанали от всякакъв вид и тип"
}
```

4.2 Twitter

Text from tweets is usually noisy, so we are preprocessing and cleaning the input text to remove symbols such as (@, #, etc). Tweets are usually very different from other forms of comments or text on social media, because they are restricted to 280 characters and tend to be more opinionated than other forms. The roberta model has been used for sentiment analysis, while we used the deberta model for emotion analysis which shows to have higher accuracy. Supported languages English(en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), Bulgarian (bg).

Endpoint: /sentiment/twitter

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: /emotion/twitter

- Labels: love, joy, sadness, surprise, anger, fear

Example 3:

In the third example, we have as input in Twitter API endpoints a tweet in Portuguese, from [@TurismodeLisboa](#) Twitter account.

The output of the API responses has identified the language as Portuguese, and has classified the sentiment as “positive” with a score of 92% and the emotion as “joy” with a score of 98%.

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/sentiment/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Lisboa sempre inspiradora e especial."
  }'
```

Comment translation from Portuguese to English:

Lisbon always inspiring and special.

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "pt",
  "label": "positive",
  "score": 0.9261,
  "text": "Lisboa sempre inspiradora e especial."
}
```

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/emotion/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Lisboa sempre inspiradora e especial."
  }'
```

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "pt",
  "label": "joy",
  "score": 0.9822,
  "text": "Lisboa sempre inspiradora e especial."
}
```

Example 4:

Example 4 provides as input in Twitter API endpoints a tweet in Greek form [@AthensMayor](#) Twitter account.

We can see in the output of the API responses that the sentiment of the text has been classified as “negative” with a 76% score and the detected emotion is “anger” with a 28% score. The language of the text has been identified as Greek.

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/sentiment/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Έχει εγκαταλείψει ολόκληρες περιοχές στην Αθήνα: Πλ.Καραϊσκάκη, Πλ. Βικτωρίας,
    Πατήσια, Κυψέλη, Ομόνοια... και θέλει να ανοικοδομήσει το Κίεβο!"
  }'
```

Tweet translation from Greek to English:

He has abandoned entire areas in Athens: Karaiskaki Square, Victoria Square, Patisia, Kypseli, Omonia... and he wants to rebuild Kyiv!

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "el",
  "label": "negative",
  "score": 0.7645,
  "text": "Έχει εγκαταλείψει ολόκληρες περιοχές στην Αθήνα: Πλ.Καραϊσκάκη, Πλ. Βικτωρίας,
  Πατήσια, Κυψέλη, Ομόνοια... και θέλει να ανοικοδομήσει το Κίεβο!"
}
```

Request:

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/emotion/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
    "text": "Έχει εγκαταλείψει ολόκληρες περιοχές στην Αθήνα: Πλ.Καραϊσκάκη, Πλ. Βικτωρίας,
    Πατήσια, Κυψέλη, Ομόνοια... και θέλει να ανοικοδομήσει το Κίεβο!"
  }'
```

Response:

```
{
  "lang": "el",
```

```

"label": "anger",
"score": 0.2849,
"text": "Έχει εγκαταλείψει ολόκληρες περιοχές στην Αθήνα: Πλ.Καραϊσκάκη, Πλ. Βικτωρίας, Πατήσια, Κυψέλη, Ομόνοια... και θέλει να ανοικοδομήσει το Κίεβο!"
}

```

Example 5:

Example 5 is a tweet in English from the [@visitcyprus](#) Twitter account.

The output shows the sentiment of the text as “neutral” with a 52% score and the emotion as “joy” with a 94% score. Also, the language of the text has been identified as English.

Request:

```

curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/sentiment/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
  "text": "I wish that the Cypriot Government declares it as a National Park for future generations to enjoy, as a taxpayer I would not object if the property owners were duly compensated for any potential loss via developers who focus is profit rather than the eco system."
}'

```

Response:

```

{
  "Lang": "en",
  "Label": "neutral",
  "score": 0.5251,
  "text": "I wish that the Cypriot Government declares it as a National Park for future generations to enjoy, as a taxpayer I would not object if the property owners were duly compensated for any potential loss via developers who focus is profit rather than the eco system."
}

```

Request:

```

curl -X 'POST' \
  'https://ai4pp.reportbrain.com/emotion/twitter' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'X-API-KEY: $TOKEN' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{
  "text": "I wish that the Cypriot Government declares it as a National Park for future generations to enjoy, as a taxpayer I would not object if the property owners were duly compensated for any potential loss via developers who focus is profit rather than the eco

```

```
system."  
'
```

Response:

```
{  
  "Lang": "en",  
  "Label": "joy",  
  "score": 0.9402,  
  "text": "I wish that the Cypriot Government declares it as a National Park for future  
generations to enjoy, as a taxpayer I would not object if the property owners were duly  
compensated for any potential loss via developers who focus is profit rather than the eco  
system."  
}
```

5 Conclusion

This document describes the work undertaken by Reportbrain as part of the AI4PP project for D5.1."AI Tools and Technologies V1", The deliverable includes a detailed description of the methodology, models and architecture used for a software as a service solution. The goal of the document is for the user to be able to understand and use the service, provided they have access either to the VPME platform or obtained access in accordance with the AI4PP policies.

The next steps will be concentrated on the development of task 5.2. "Text Analytics", which focuses on information extraction from text. The first part of 5.2, which is in "work in progress" stage, is the Named Entity Extraction (NER) that will be able to extract names and organizations for the available languages in the pilots. More information about task 5.2. will be provided in a later version of this document.

6 References

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